

Speculation on the Photon Solution from Maxwell's EM Equations Part II

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As noted in Part I, the mathematical derivation of the existence of a photon in Maxwell's EM equations is demonstrated through the existence of two wave equations, one for E (electric field) and the other for B (magnetic field). This, in turn, is based on two specific Maxwell equations.

In Part I, we argued that the form: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ already suggests a wave solution because there exists a periodic function $f(-\omega t + kx)$ which makes $E=0$ and $B=0$, namely $\phi = f(-\omega t + kx)$ and $A = f(-\omega t + kx) (1,0,0)$. This may be readily altered to: $\phi = f(-\omega t + kx)$ and $A = \phi (1,1,1)$ to obtain E and B fields of the same magnitude and perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion. We also suggested that a solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is associated with conservation of energy, momentum and spatial probability, a feature which is not apparent from $E = \cos(-\omega t + kx) e_i$ (example) from the wave equation.

In Part I, we noted that the form $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ follows from a desire to have the vector part of E depend on the natural vector in the moving frame, namely: $\{ (x-vt), y, z \}$. If one uses $-\text{grad } \phi$ (which holds in the rest frame of a point charge), the vector portion is: $\{ \gamma(x-vt), y, z \}$ where $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. This is not the spatial vector that a person in the moving frame would see or measure, but E is in fact measured. In order to remove γ , one requires the addition of $-\frac{dA}{dt}$.

Although conservation of energy, momentum and spatial probability are key and linked with $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, we suggest that there is an extra feature which is directly linked to the use of $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$. This form ensures a usual measurement of an r vector in the moving frame and at the same time provides for a mathematical solution of an entity which is able to provide both a ruler and clock, namely $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, because: $\omega = 2\pi f$ and $T = 1/f$ and wavelength = $1/k$. Thus, the suggestion that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ existing because of a measurement criterion (usual r vector) is actually physically linked to a measurement entity. Thus, one does not simply have an abstract condition requiring a usual vector, but it is enforced physically by the existence of a photon which provides for this measurement, we argue.

$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ ((1))

In Part I, we noted that $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the rest frame and that $(0, \phi) \rightarrow (A, \phi)$ ($c=1$). We further argued that $-\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame cannot be the full expression E for a very specific reason which does not require the use of other Maxwell EM equations. In particular, the usual way of obtaining ((1)) is to use two of Maxwell's equations, which are said to follow directly from experimental observation, i.e.

$\text{Grad } \cdot E = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density ((2a))}$ and $\text{grad } \times E = \frac{dB}{dt}$ ((2b))

If one expects that: $E = -\text{grad } \phi + N$, then $\text{grad } \times N = \frac{d}{dt} B$, but $B = \text{grad } \times A$, so

$N = \frac{dA}{dt}$ ((3))

We do not use this approach, but argue that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ follows from a measurement condition. We argue that this viewpoint is important because measurement is central in physics. In fact, if the argument of justifying ((1)) on the basis of measurement alone is legitimate, there should be a physical confirmation. We argue that the existence of the photon is, in fact, this confirmation.

The measurement argument given in Part I (and also in a previous note) is the following. In the rest frame, $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, with:

$$\phi = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \cdot 1/\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad ((4)) \text{ so that Gauss' law holds:}$$

$$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad } \phi = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \delta \text{ function}(x=0,y=0,z=0) \quad ((5))$$

In the moving frame: $(0, \phi) \rightarrow$ Lorentz transforms $\rightarrow (A, \phi)$ where $\phi = g \phi(x, y, z)$ and $A = v g \phi$ with $v =$ velocity in the x direction so A is $g v \phi(1, 0, 0)$.

ϕ transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector, because $q \phi$ ($q =$ test charge) is potential energy which is like rest mass.

The question becomes: What is E , the electric field in the moving frame?

One might suggest: $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, but this leads to:

$$-\text{grad } \phi = \{ g(x-vt), y, z \} / [g(x-vt)(x-vt) + y^2 + z^2]^{1.5} \quad ((6))$$

The problem, we argue, is that the vector portion: $\{ g(x-vt), y, z \}$ is not the usual r vector one would measure in the moving frame. The measurable vector is $\{ (x-vt), y, z \}$. Nobody would measure r , take the x component and multiply it by g as a measuring process. The point we wish to make is that E is a measurable quantity, including the vector portion, in the moving frame.

We suggest that to make E compatible with a measurable an extra piece is needed, and we argued for dA/dt partial in Part I (see details there). This in fact removes g using $A = v g \phi(x, y, z)$ (x direction). E , as stated, is a measurable quantity.

We used a measurement argument to justify its form: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, but we argued in Part I, that this allows for a solution $\phi = f(-wt + kx)$. The argument $-wt + kx$ is readily recognized as that of a wave. In fact, in Part I, we show that $\phi = f(-wt + kx)$ with $A = \phi(1, 0, 0)$ yields $E = B = 0$, while $\phi = f(-wt + kx)$ with $A = \phi(1, 1, 1)$ leads to $|E| = |B|$ and E and B perpendicular to each other in a plane perpendicular to motion.

We suggested in Part I that $f(-wt + kx)$ be periodic, but that this leads to a periodic energy density and Poynting momentum density:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \text{ and Poynting momentum density} = 1/\mu_0 E \times B \quad ((7))$$

Periodic values violate conservation of energy and momentum and require the taking of averages. We suggested instead that one represent the entity by $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and argued that this conserves energy, momentum and spatial density (see Part I for the full argument).

The point we raise here is that conservation of energy, momentum and spatial density is critical, but what is the link with measurement of an r vector needed in describing a physical electric field? It is the measurement of r requirement which leads to the form $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ in the first place, we argue, and it is from this result that one postulates $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, i.e. the existence of a photon. The requirement and the photon should be linked, i.e. both should be associated with measurement, we argue, in order to have consistency.

If the measurement (r vector form) is critical and leads to an $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, one may ask: What does $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ have to do with measurement?

We argue that it provides a clock and a ruler. In other words, $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ may be seen as being essential to measurement. The measurement requirement leading to ((1)) leads to the solution of a physical entity which creates the means of measurement, i.e. provides a ruler and clock. The clock follows from $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 3.14f$ where period = $T = 1/f$ and wavelength = $1/k$.

Thus, we argue that the measurement criterion, namely that E is a measurable vector, depends on the measurable physical vector $(x-vt, y, z)$ and also physically provides a means of making this measurement.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the traditional approach to obtaining a photon solution from Maxwell's equations is to obtain a wave equation for E and another for B with charge and current density sources set to 0. There is nothing wrong with such an approach, but we note that the photon solution $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ introduces a measurement mechanism because $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 3.14 \cdot \text{frequency}$ and period = $T = 1/\text{frequency}$, while wavelength = $1/k$. Given that the photon is essentially a ruler and clock, why isn't the argument for its existence based on a measurement criterion?

We argue here that in fact it is. We note that $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in a rest frame and that $(0, \phi)$ Lorentz transforms $\rightarrow (A, \phi)$ where $\phi = g \phi$, $g = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $A = v e_i g \phi$ where e_i is the unit vector in the x direction. Using Gauss' law, one may show that $\phi = q/(4\pi \epsilon_0) / \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$.

One might suggest that $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame. The problem is that E (electric field) is a measurable quantity, including the vector part, and $-\text{grad } \phi$ leads to a vector portion of: $\{g g(x-vt), y, z\}$. Such a vector is not measured in the moving frame, rather $(x-vt, y, z)$ is. As a result, we argued in Part I that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ in order to have $(x-vt, y, z)$ as the vector portion. In other words, a measurement argument is solely responsible for the form of E . At the same time, this E form gives rise to a periodic solution $f(-\omega t + kx)$ which may lead to $E=0, B=0$ if $A = f(-\omega t + kx) (1, 0, 0)$, but leads to an entity if $\phi = f(-\omega t + kx)$, $A = f(-\omega t + kx) (1, 1, 1)$. If one chooses $f(-\omega t + kx) = \cos(-\omega t + kx)$, then ω is average em field energy and k , average Poynting momentum. Furthermore, $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ represents a kind of unusual probability which allows for conservation of energy, momentum and spatial probability.

A measurement argument leads to $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ partial which in turn leads to a photon solution. We argue that the photon itself should be linked to measurement in order to justify the measurement argument used to create ((1)) which yields its existence.

In fact, we stress here is that $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ provides a clock and ruler which are needed for measurement, namely $\omega = 2\pi f$, $T = 1/f$ and wavelength = $1/k$. Thus, the criterion that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ partial exists solely on the basis of a measurable vector at the same time gives rise to a physical entity, the photon, which may be used to make this measurement.